

RESPONSE PAPER

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)*The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:*The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMARY ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following documents is not a component of dissertation research prepared by students conducting dissertation research?

- Dissertation concept paper.
- Dissertation prospectus.
- The Personal Reflection or Journal of the student's research journey.¹**
- Dissertation manuscript.

2. The dissertation concept paper includes the following sections except:

- Theoretical Analysis of the research topic.²**
- Introduction (What will be included in the paper by the headings indicated as follows).

¹ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition)* (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 1.

² Ibid., 2.

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- Statement of the Problem.
- Research Questions.

3. **A dissertation concept paper (sometimes referred to as a pre-prospectus paper), which is a brief twelve-to-fifteen-page research proposal, describes the following.**

- What might be studied in the proposed dissertation.
- Why it needs to be studied.
- How long it will take to study it.**³
- How it might be studied.

4. **Which of the following should not be relevant to the researcher when considering the goals of both theoretical (either to contribute new knowledge or extend current theory to a new area) and applied (to use knowledge to contribute directly to the understanding of a problem or generate a solution for the problem) research?**

- Is my worldview aligned with a qualitative research approach, and also, does my intended research problem “fit” with qualitative research?
- Does my intended research problem “fit” with quantitative research?**⁴
- Do the problem, the purpose of the study, and the research questions have the potential to serve the goal of the research, either applied or theoretical?
- Is there sufficient theory to explain the phenomenon, or a reasonable solution to the research problem, sometimes referred to as the “so what?” test?

5. **While reading about researching a topic, it is important that you do not follow this particular question.**

- What do I already know about the topic, and also what do I need to read and know to write the essay?

³ Ibid.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 240.

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- How can I copy this material directly into my work?**⁵
- Is this material useful to my topic/argument?
- Can I use this material to support my answer?

6. What are the components of an excellent literature review?

- Excessive information on a particular topic gathered from Wikipedia is credible enough for an excellent literature review.
- A literature review documents a detailed review of past research. It summarises known facts to determine what is unknown concerning the research topic and arguments in the literature and provides study rationale.**⁶
- This critical activity allows for a brief understanding of the research activity and the projected input of the study.
- It is a paraphrase compilation of all recognised published work related to the study.

7. How best can you summarise the whole research in a written article of about 500 words?

- The abstract gives initial impressions of a research article, accurate and meticulously drafted, with detailed findings and conclusions.
- Abstracts are generally within a defined word count. The abstract summarises the study, including the problem statement, purpose, scope, data sources, methodology, essential findings, and inference.**⁷
- An abstract is a very brief portion of an article that includes speciality jargon that may be difficult to read and even harder to understand.
- The abstract should detail your entire project and be written before the rest of the paper.

8. Using the Turabian Author-Date citation style, how do you reference a single-authored book?

⁵ Ibid., 46.

⁶ Ibid., 70–80.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 1110–1115.

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- Author's last name, Author's first name, Date (parentheses), Title (quotation mark), Editor(s)/Translator(s), Place, Publication Press.
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- Author's last name, Author's first name, Edition (if existing), Date, Title (italics), Editor(s)/Translator(s) (if existing), Place: Publication Press.⁸**

9. The solution to avoiding Plagiarism is to:

- Direct Copying Without Attribution: Using someone else's words, sentences, or entire paragraphs exactly as they are without quotation marks or giving credit to the original author.
- Paraphrasing Without Acknowledgment: Rephrasing someone else's ideas or work without proper attribution, even if the words are changed, but the original idea or structure remains intact.
- Properly CITE the author or source that has provided the information you are using.⁹**
- Using Another's Work as Your Own: Submitting someone else's work, such as essays, research, or projects, as if you created it, whether purchased, downloaded, or borrowed from a friend or online source, without acknowledgment.

10. The following are correct about full stop except.

- A full stop marks the end of a sentence.
- All footnotes end with a full stop, except those consisting solely of an internet or email address.

⁸ Ibid., 45, 136.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack, Period 1*, Fifth Edition, (Washington, D.C: Euclid University Press, 2024), 38.

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- All footnotes end with a full stop, including those consisting solely of an internet or email address.¹⁰
- Do not use a full stop at the end of a heading.

11. Which of these is not correct about question mark?

- Every question which expects a separate answer should be followed by a question mark.
- The next word after a question mark should begin with a capital letter.
- An indirect question.¹¹
- There should be no space between the question mark and the preceding word, letter or number.

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English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union. European Commission, 2011.

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¹⁰ *English Style Guide. A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Union* (European Commission, 2011), 9.

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¹¹ *Ibid.*, 15.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.